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Cervical cancer cell line transcriptomics.

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We used RNA-sequencing for transcriptomic discovery of genes important for the cancer cell in cervical cancer using precise measurement of total gene expression in cultured cells. We report here discovery of *Gpr161* as a specific marker of cervical cancer cells, a gene whose expression could completely distinguish Raji cells from C33A, HeLa and CaSki cells.

Citations

1. Mukhopadhyay, S., Wen, X., Ratti, N., Loktev, A., Rangell, L., Scales, S.J. and Jackson, P.K., 2013. The ciliary G-protein-coupled receptor Gpr161 negatively regulates the Sonic hedgehog pathway via cAMP signaling. *Cell*, 152(1), pp.210-223.

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